

ABSTRACT

The scope of this paper is to give a new generalization to δ -closed sets namely λ_g^δ -closed sets which involves the use of two different operators. Some interesting theorems involving λ_g^δ -closed sets are discussed.

KEYWORDS: δ -closed sets, δg -closed sets, $g\delta$ -closed sets, δg^* -closed sets, (Λ, δ) -closed sets, λ_g^δ -closed sets

INTRODUCTION

Ever since the notion of δ -closed sets in topological spaces was introduced by Velicko in 1968, several authors started to extend this concept via various types of generalizations^{[1][2][3][4][5][9][12]}. As an outcome of these generalizations, various forms of closed sets and interesting separation axioms came into existence. In 2004, Georgiou discussed a unique type of generalization of δ -closed set namely (Λ, δ) -closed set which is defined as the intersection of a Λ_δ -set and a δ -closed set. A subset A of a topological space (X, τ) is called a Λ_δ -set if $\Lambda_\delta(A)=A$, where $\Lambda_\delta(A)$ is the intersection of all δ -open sets containing A . Λ_δ plays the role of an operator which is an alternative to the classical closure operator. In this paper, we have portrayed a new variety of generalization involving the classical closure operator and the operator Λ which is defined to be the intersection of all open sets containing A . The outcome of such a generalization is named to be λ_g^δ -closed sets. We have discussed the relationship of λ_g^δ -closed sets with some already existing sets in the literature followed by some interesting characterizations using few already existing spaces. Finally, the notion of λ_g^δ -open sets and some properties are discussed.

PREREQUISITES

Definition 2.1: A subset A of a topological space (X, τ) is called

- (1) **regular open**[11] if $\text{int}(\text{cl}(A))=A$.
- (2) **δ -open**[14] if it is the union of regular open sets, the complement of δ -open is called δ -closed.
- (3) **Λ_δ -set** [5] if $\Lambda_\delta(A)=A$, where $\Lambda_\delta(A)=\bigcap\{O \in \delta O(X, \tau) \mid A \subseteq O\}$.
- (4) **(Λ, δ) -closed**[5] if $A = T \cap C$, where T is a Λ_δ -set and C is a δ -closed set.
- (5) **δg -closed**[2] if $\text{cl}_\delta(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is open in (X, τ)
- (6) **δg^* -closed**[3] if $\text{cl}_\delta(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is δ -open in (X, τ) .
- (7) **$g\delta$ -closed**[3] if $\text{cl}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is δ -open in (X, τ) .
- (8) **δg_s -closed**[6] if $\delta\text{-scl}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is δ -open in (X, τ) .
- (9) **$g\delta_s$ -closed**[1] if $\text{scl}(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is δ -open in (X, τ) .

Remark: The class of all regular closed (resp. δ -closed, (Λ, δ) -closed) sets are denoted by $\text{RC}(X, \tau)$ (resp. $\delta C(X, \tau)$, $(\Lambda, \delta)C(X, \tau)$).

Definition 2.2: A subset A of a topological space (X, τ) is called

- (1) **weakly Hausdorff**[13] if every singleton is δ -closed.

- (2) $T_{3/4}$ -space[2] if every δg -closed set is δ -closed in (X, τ) .
- (3) δ -door space[13] if every subset of (X, τ) is either δ -open or δ -closed in (X, τ) .
- (4) T_δ -space[3] if every $g\delta$ -closed set is δ -closed in (X, τ) .
- (5) $\delta T_{3/4}$ -space[1] if every $g\delta s$ -closed set is δ -closed in (X, τ) .

λ_g^δ -CLOSED SETS IN TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

Definition 3.1: A subset A of a topological space (X, τ) is called λ_g^δ -closed set if $cl_\delta(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is (Λ, δ) -open in X . The family of all λ_g^δ -closed sets of (X, τ) is denoted by $\lambda_g^\delta C(X, \tau)$.

Proposition 3.2: Every δ -closed set is λ_g^δ -closed but not conversely.

Proof: Let A be a δ -closed set and U be a (Λ, δ) -open set containing A . Since A is δ -closed, $cl_\delta(A) = A$. Therefore $cl_\delta(A) = A \subseteq U$ and hence A is λ_g^δ -closed.

Counter example 3.3: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$, $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}\}$. Take $A = \{a\}$ then A is λ_g^δ -closed but not δ -closed as $\delta C(X, \tau) = \{X, \phi\}$.

Proposition 3.4: Every λ_g^δ -closed set is δg^* -closed but not conversely.

Proof: Let A be a λ_g^δ -closed set and U be a δ -open set containing A . Since every δ -open set is (Λ, δ) -open[5] and A is λ_g^δ -closed, $cl_\delta(A) \subseteq U$. Therefore A is δg^* -closed.

Counter example 3.5: Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$, $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$. Take $A = \{a, c\}$ then A is δg^* -closed but not λ_g^δ -closed.

Proposition 3.6: Every λ_g^δ -closed set is $g\delta$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof: Since $cl(A) \subseteq cl_\delta(A)$, the proof follows that of Proposition 3.4.

Counter example 3.7: Let X and τ be defined as in Example 3.5. Take $A = \{b\}$ then A is $g\delta$ -closed but not λ_g^δ -closed.

Proposition 3.8: Every λ_g^δ -closed set is $\delta g s$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof: Since $\delta\text{-scl}(A) \subseteq cl_\delta(A)$, the proof follows that of Proposition 3.4.

Counter example 3.9: Let X, τ and A be defined as in Example 3.7 then A is $\delta g s$ -closed but not λ_g^δ -closed.

Proposition 3.10: Every λ_g^δ -closed set is $g\delta s$ -closed but not conversely.

Proof: Since $\text{scl}(A) \subseteq cl_\delta(A)$, the proof follows that of Proposition 3.4.

Counter example 3.11: Let X, τ and A be defined as in Example 3.7 then A is $g\delta s$ -closed but not λ_g^δ -closed.

The newly defined family of λ_g^δ -closed sets properly fits between the family of δ -closed sets and δg^* -closed sets as observed from the following link.

Remark 3.12: Closedness (resp. g -closedness, α -closedness, semi-closedness, pre-closedness, δg -closedness) is independent of λ_g^δ -closedness as observed from the following examples.

Example 3.13: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, c, d\}\}$. Take $A = \{a, b, d\}$ then A is closed (resp. g -closed, α -closed, semi-closed, pre-closed and δg -closed) but not λ_g^δ -closed in (X, τ) .

Example 3.14: Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\tau = \{X, \phi, \{a\}\}$. Take $A = \{a\}$ then A is λ_g^δ -closed but not closed (resp. g -closed, α -closed, semi-closed, pre-closed and δg -closed) in (X, τ) .

Theorem 3.15: Let A be a λ_g^δ -closed set in (X, τ) . Then $\text{cl}_\delta(A) - A$ does not contain a non-empty (Λ, δ) -closed set.

Proof: Suppose that A is λ_g^δ -closed and let F be a (Λ, δ) -closed set contained in $\text{cl}_\delta(A) - A$. Now F^c is a (Λ, δ) -open set in X such that $A \subseteq F^c$. Since A is a λ_g^δ -closed, $\text{cl}_\delta(A) \subseteq F^c$. Thus $F \subseteq (\text{cl}_\delta(A))^c$. Also $F \subseteq \text{cl}_\delta(A) - A$. Therefore $F \subseteq (\text{cl}_\delta(A))^c \cap \text{cl}_\delta(A) = \phi$. Hence $F = \phi$.

Proposition 3.16: If A is a (Λ, δ) -open set and a λ_g^δ -closed set of (X, τ) then A is a δ -closed set of X .

Proof: Since A is (Λ, δ) -open and λ_g^δ -closed, $\text{cl}_\delta(A) \subseteq A$. Hence A is δ -closed.

Theorem 3.17: If A is a λ_g^δ -closed set and (Λ, δ) -open and F is δ -closed in (X, τ) , then $A \cap F$ is δ -closed.

Proof: Since A is λ_g^δ -closed and (Λ, δ) -open, A is δ -closed by Proposition 3.16. Since F is δ -closed in X , $A \cap F$ is δ -closed in X .

Proposition 3.18: If A is a λ_g^δ -closed set in (X, τ) and $A \subseteq B \subseteq \text{cl}_\delta(A)$, then B is also a λ_g^δ -closed set.

Proof: Let U be a (Λ, δ) -open set of X containing B . Then $A \subseteq U$. Since A is λ_g^δ -closed, $\text{cl}_\delta(A) \subseteq U$. Also since $B \subseteq \text{cl}_\delta(A)$, $\text{cl}_\delta(B) \subseteq \text{cl}_\delta(\text{cl}_\delta(A)) = \text{cl}_\delta(A)$. Hence $\text{cl}_\delta(B) \subseteq U$ and therefore B is λ_g^δ -closed.

Theorem 3.19: Let A be a λ_g^δ -closed set of (X, τ) . Then A is δ -closed iff $\text{cl}_\delta(A) - A$ is (Λ, δ) -closed.

Proof: Necessity: Let A be a δ -closed subset of (X, τ) . Then $\text{cl}_\delta(A) = A$ and so $\text{cl}_\delta(A) - A = \phi$, which is (Λ, δ) -closed.

Sufficiency: Let $\text{cl}_\delta(A) - A$ be (Λ, δ) -closed. Since A is λ_g^δ -closed, by Theorem 3.15, $\text{cl}_\delta(A) - A$ does not contain a non-empty (Λ, δ) -closed set which implies $\text{cl}_\delta(A) - A = \phi$. Therefore $\text{cl}_\delta(A) = A$ and hence A is δ -closed.

Characterizations of λ_g^δ -closed sets through existing spaces

Proposition 3.20: In a $T_{3/4}$ -space, every δg -closed set is λ_g^δ -closed.

Proof: Let (X, τ) be a $T_{3/4}$ -space and let A be a δg -closed set in (X, τ) . In $T_{3/4}$ -space, the class of all δg -closed sets coincide with that of δ -closed sets. Therefore A is δ -closed in (X, τ) . Moreover, every δ -closed set is λ_g^δ -closed and hence A is λ_g^δ -closed in (X, τ) .

Proposition 3.21: In a δ -door space, every subset is either λ_g^δ -open or λ_g^δ -closed.

Proof: Let A be a subset of (X, τ) which is a δ -door space. Then every subset is either δ -open or δ -closed. Since every δ -open or δ -closed is λ_g^δ -open or λ_g^δ -closed respectively, we have A is either λ_g^δ -open or λ_g^δ -closed.

Proposition 3.22: In a weakly Hausdorff space, every singleton is λ_g^δ -closed.

Proof: Let (X, τ) be a weakly Hausdorff space. Then every singleton is δ -closed. Since every δ -closed set is λ_g^δ -closed, we have that every singleton is λ_g^δ -closed.

Proposition 3.23: The family of all $g\delta$ -closed sets and that of λ_g^δ -closed sets coincide in a T_δ -space.

Proof: Let A be a λ_g^δ -closed set. By Proposition 3.6, every λ_g^δ -closed set is a $g\delta$ -closed set. Therefore A is $g\delta$ -closed. Conversely, let A be $g\delta$ -closed. In T_δ -space, every $g\delta$ -closed set is δ -closed. Since every δ -closed set is λ_g^δ -closed, we have A is λ_g^δ -closed.

Proposition 3.24: In a $\delta T_{3/4}$ -space, the family of all $g\delta$ s-closed sets and that of λ_g^δ -closed sets coincide.

Proof: Let A be a λ_g^δ -closed set. By Proposition 3.10, every λ_g^δ -closed set is a $g\delta$ s-closed set. Therefore A is $g\delta$ s-closed. Conversely, let A be $g\delta$ s-closed. In $\delta T_{3/4}$ -space, every $g\delta$ s-closed set is δ -closed. Since every δ -closed set is λ_g^δ -closed, we have A is λ_g^δ -closed.

4. λ_g^δ -OPEN SETS IN TOPOLOGICAL SPACES

Definition 4.1: A subset A of a topological space (X, τ) is called **λ_g^δ -open** if its complement A^c is λ_g^δ -closed in (X, τ) . The family of all λ_g^δ -open sets in (X, τ) is denoted by $\lambda_g^\delta O(X, \tau)$.

Lemma 4.2:[12] For a subset A of (X, τ) , $cl_\delta(X \setminus A) = X \setminus int_\delta(A)$.

Theorem 4.3: A subset A of a topological space (X, τ) is λ_g^δ -open if and only if $G \subseteq int_\delta(A)$ whenever $G \subseteq A$ and G is (Λ, δ) -closed.

Proof: Necessity: Assume that A is λ_g^δ -open. Then A^c is λ_g^δ -closed. Let G be a (Λ, δ) -closed set in (X, τ) such that $G \subseteq A$. Then G^c is (Λ, δ) -open in (X, τ) such that $A^c \subseteq G^c$. Since A^c is λ_g^δ -closed, $cl_\delta(A^c) \subseteq G^c$, equivalently $G \subseteq int_\delta(A)$.

Sufficiency: Conversely, assume that $G \subseteq int_\delta(A)$, whenever $G \subseteq A$ and G is (Λ, δ) -closed in (X, τ) . Let $A^c \subseteq F$, where F is (Λ, δ) -open. Then $F^c \subseteq A$. By criteria, $F^c \subseteq int_\delta(A) \Rightarrow cl_\delta(A^c) \subseteq F$. Thus A^c is λ_g^δ -closed and hence A is λ_g^δ -open.

Proposition 4.4: If $int_\delta(A) \subseteq B \subseteq A$ and A is λ_g^δ -open in (X, τ) , then B is λ_g^δ -open in (X, τ) .

Proof: It follows from Lemma 4.2 and Proposition 3.19.

Theorem 4.5: If A is λ_g^δ -open in X if and only if $G = X$ whenever G is (Λ, δ) -open and $int_\delta(A) \cup A^c \subseteq G$.

Proof: Necessity: Let A be λ_g^δ -open set and G be (Λ, δ) -open and $int_\delta(A) \cup A^c \subseteq G$. This implies $G^c \subseteq (int_\delta(A) \cup A^c)^c = (int_\delta(A))^c \cap A = (int_\delta(A))^c \setminus A^c = cl_\delta(A^c) \setminus A^c$. Since A^c is λ_g^δ -closed and G^c is (Λ, δ) -closed by Theorem 3.15, it follows that $G^c = \phi$ and hence $G = X$.

Sufficiency: Suppose that F is (Λ, δ) -closed and $F \subseteq A$. Then $int_\delta(A) \cup A^c \subseteq G \subseteq int_\delta(A) \cup F^c \subseteq G$. Since δ -open $\Rightarrow (\Lambda, \delta)$ -open, we get $int_\delta(A)$ is (Λ, δ) -open and F^c is (Λ, δ) -open. Hence $int_\delta(A) \cup F^c$ is (Λ, δ) -open. By hypothesis, $int_\delta(A) \cup F^c = X$ and hence $F \subseteq int_\delta(A)$. Therefore by Proposition 4.4, A is λ_g^δ -open in X .

Proposition 4.6: For each $a \in X$ either $\{a\}$ is (Λ, δ) -closed or $\{a\}$ is λ_g^δ -open in (X, τ) . That is, for any space (X, τ) , $X = (\Lambda, \delta)C(X, \tau) \cup \lambda_g^\delta O(X, \tau)$.

Proof: Suppose that $\{a\}$ is not (Λ, δ) -closed then $\{a\}^c$ is not (Λ, δ) -open and the only (Λ, δ) -open set containing $\{a\}^c$ is the space X itself. That is, $\{a\}^c \subseteq X$. Therefore, $cl_\delta(\{a\}^c) \subseteq X$ and so $\{a\}^c$ is λ_g^δ -closed and hence $\{a\}$ is λ_g^δ -open.

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